

The “Event Horizon concept” dataset gathering and authoring system

The Authors here describe the “Event Horizon concept” as a shared multi-contributor knowledge database devoted to authoritatively accumulate info(s) on whatever occurred event by a .app-like multimedia interface running on an individual smart device also available for less instructed or disabled persons (see: “Event Horizon concept” working scheme).

The system supports the operator(s) *Lifelong learning* and *Experiential Learning* by structuring and sharing with the Authors(s) via IT & IoT the data that the operator(s) gather(s) time by time or event by event.

The expert(s) Authors validate the data and restate to the operator(s) their authoritative opinion(s) on the event(s) on the shared data. Experts may also support the operator by suggesting approaches to dataset collection or event(s) scrutiny.

The System works as a free mutual data & services sharing between 1) the operator(s) that submit the data they gather to the Authors (s) and 2) the Authors that restate their interpretation(s) to the operator(s).

The system is built in a way that the data and the interpretations remain available for Authors and solely the interpretations for the operators. The system may also run by the economical use of the concept in case of agreement among the actors of the interaction, i.e. one/several Authors(s) one/several operator(s) for the use of a subset of the System accumulated dataset.

The very first operating version of the “Event Horizon concept” goes back to 2013 allowing to manage data collection (see screen 1, below), taxa identification (see screen 2, below), and hardware for field work checklist and suggestions (see screen 3 below).

Screen 1,

Screen 2,

Screen 3.

“Event Horizon concept” working scheme

